

PACIFICUS

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“GLACE BRIMMING WITH GRACE”

Since then, she has been a woman of grace.
With a genuine mind and heart in its place.
She brightens the night with her generosity.
Her personality stayed grounded, and an illuminated beacon blazed vibrantly.

Amidst the challenges that life has brought,
She is resilient.
She meets the storm with empowerment and compassion.
With anger and tears, her heart stays warm.

Despite the passage of time, she remains loyal.
She has white hair and is getting wrinkles.
Her beauty is timeless, both inside and out.
She is, indeed, true to life.

A woman I value, with wisdom so deep.
A mother's love is a treasure to hold dear.
She has a soul so divine, a woman of a lifetime,
I am referring to her as "Mother Glace, brimming with Grace."